

Resilience through Self-Sufficiency in Smart Cities: A Preliminary Bucharest Use Case

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Abstract—Cities follow new trends towards advanced social and technological development. The Smart City concept includes many innovative aspects, but an essential one is the capability to generate its own clean energy, leading to an increased energy resilience and immunity against major disturbances, as a mitigation of the negative impact of global warming related extreme weather, but also of other blackout inducing events, such as cyber-attacks or evolving faults. The paper presents an assessment for both clean energy production using PVs and resilience, applied for Bucharest city and its neighbour zone of Ilfov county, showing the conditions for obtaining up to 100% renewable production and high resilience. In this paper, a financial analyse is also performed to check the feasibility of the scenarios, with or without using large storage resources, by achieving different levels of self-sufficiency¹.

Index Terms—renewable energy sources, resilience, self-sufficiency, Smart City

I. INTRODUCTION

AS major pillars of the world economy, many cities have experienced asocial and technological development in recent decades. The demographic transition of urban areas has brought with it a number of new challenges in terms of resource management, especially related to energy consumption. Responsible for more than 75% of global primary energy consumption and 80% of GHG emissions [1], urban communities have already begun to take action regarding energy generation, storage and infrastructure planning.

The sustainable strategies implementation is crucial for developing the cities of the future. Given the increased focus on greenhouse gas reduction, Smart Grid solutions, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and the emerging Internet of Things, set the foundation for this energy revolution, by enabling the integration and monitoring of distributed generation in urban districts. Becoming 100% renewable and producing as much as possible locally is a new trend in today's efforts for achieving drastic measures against climate change, as well as smart cities resilience. PV power generation technologies and fuel cells based on green gas prove themselves promising assets to achieve this ambitious goal. Highly decentralized, this emerging renewable solution finds its applications in most fundamental components of a sustainable city. From urban street-lightning, electrical vehicle charging, energy efficiency enhancement for

buildings, to significant reduction of grid losses, solar solutions can play an important role in increasing reliability of power supply services. The past years events have revealed a new vulnerability of cities related to power supply in special situations, asking for resilience against the major outages. Natural disasters or terrorist attacks have led to long-lasting disruptions with severe social and economic impact. These facts have encouraged the amplification of studies and investments in the concept of resilience of smart cities. Under these circumstances, PV can represent an important source of self-sufficiency, by covering energy demand (completely or partially – at least for critical loads) during a major interruption. Potential disasters due to climate change and cyber-threats can be combined in some areas with the danger of earthquakes. City resilience is also specifically considered for sustainable cities and communities [2], as important value for the new smart city concept [3].

The decline of PV modules prices (80% in the last seven years [4]), their easier grid integration and the increasing climate change awareness led to solar PV deployment growth worldwide, half of which consisting in distributed generation. However, there remains plenty of potential for further expansion [5]. As IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency) mentions in [4], rooftop solar PV (including residential and commercial roofs, parking roofs etc.) represents an economically beneficial source that meets the urban electricity needs in daily activities, as well as in case of disruptive events. Additionally, to the unused roof surfaces, researchers take into account the possibility to create transparent solar panels to be placed on windows and buildings facades, in order to maximize the share of renewable energy [6].

In order to estimate urban areas solar potential, a three-dimensional analysis of buildings and shading impacts of neighbouring constructions is necessary to be performed. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) represents a useful tool in renewable energy penetration research. By offering geospatial analysis and visualization methods, GIS allows users to investigate suitable locations for solar technologies placement. Various GIS-based technologies have been approached in order to access remote sensing imagery of PV plant, such as the Geographical Resources Analysis Support System (GRASS), ArcGIS or Saga GIS [7]. However, although the GIS modules allow not only the identification of appropriate surfaces for photovoltaic panels, but also the determination of their generation capability, the calculation model is based on static geospatial data, not including dynamic variables, such as atmospheric conditions [8]. Another remote sensing technology commonly implemented is LiDAR (Light Detection And Ranging). This active methodology allows solar panel deployment analysis over

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large-scale urban areas, based on high-details scanning of surfaces topographies, using laser pulses emission.

Cities around the globe have started to assess their rooftops surface potential for solar energy deployment [9], using these technologies and different estimation models and methodologies. Numerous studies have been conducted, targeting both metropolises such as New York and Paris, as well as small and medium size cities. In [10], a hybrid methodology for estimating of rooftop solar photovoltaic potential in Mumbai City is applied, based on high-granularity land use data and GIS-based image analysis, resulting in a generation capacity with median efficiency panels that covers 12.8-20% of the daily energy demand.

The city of London recently announced the 100% renewable energy supply plan for the central district of the capital [11], obtained by combining local production (solar panels on City Corporation buildings), off-site renewable sources investment and purchases of renewable energy already available on the market. The decision clearly specifies that this will contribute to the City Corporation's energy resilience and carbon reduction. The increased resilience also means the possibility to produce as much as possible energy on-site or nearby, in the neighbourhood or close to the consumption pool (in this situation the city itself). In [12], the case of Lombok district, Utrecht / Holland, is analysed, revealing the possibility of reaching the value of 60% of electricity self-sufficiency from PV installation on all existing roofs. Using the entire available surface will represent only 6% of the municipal area.

In order to maximize the share on renewable sources in urban energy supply, an existing low-voltage feeder in Belgium is examined in [12], based on smart metering data. The proposed model aims to determine the PV hosting capacity, considering grids characteristics and local technical requirements.

Concerns about solar roof potential are found even in the US, where the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) has conducted a study on the possibility of covering energy consumption using exclusively solar panels on buildings [13]. Using LIDAR technology to measure all roof surfaces, with shadings, roof angles and orientation, the analysis shows that the technical potential of rooftop PV of all the building existing in cities boundaries (including small and medium size) is able to cover a significant percentage of energy consumption.

Fig. 1. Potential rooftop PV annual generation from all buildings as a percentage of each state's total electricity sales in 2013 [13]

For instance, Sacramento and Los Angeles may cover 72% and 60% respectively of their city consumption only

from rooftop PV. The study examines the entire US surface, as shown in Fig. 1, the final results illustrating a potential of energy generation varying from 18% to 88% of each location total electricity sales in 2013.

Grid integration of the PV production and its associated storage are not subject of this paper, however, many studies find different mitigation methods [14], [15].

Our work consists in developing a methodology for simulating the urban solar potential and estimating the distributed energy production in districts of Bucharest and nearby region. Similar to the Utrecht study case [12], the total surface usage coefficient is applied in order to calculate total power in PVs available in the city.

II. METHODOLOGY APPLIED ON BUCHAREST USE CASE

According to [16] and [17], Bucharest has a municipality area of 228 km² and an urban area of 412 km². Moreover, the Ilfov county, which can act in our study as a metropolitan area, has a surface of 2800 km². Fig. 2 illustrates the three zones by using area equivalent circles over the simplified map of Bucharest and surrounding Ilfov county.

Fig. 2. Main areas in Bucharest and neighbourhoods

The paper presents the following scenarios:

- 50% of the electricity is generated from PVs spread over the three zones;
- Entire electricity is generated from PVs spread over the three zones, meaning 100% renewable energy (RES) with PV.

For better coverage of the study subject, these two scenarios are approached in three use cases each:

- 1) a first case where no storage is considered to help the self-consumption;
- 2) a second case where storage is moderately used and allows a certain resilience;
- 3) a third situation when high deployment of storage resources is used, while the resilience increases as well.

A key performance indicator (KPI) of resilience is defined as the period of time when the city can supply its critical loads T_{RES_CL} . By resilience, we understand the possibility of the smart city to recover from a blackout and be able to have a full or a partial activity (50% or 25% percent) by supplying only critical loads. In order to be able to deduct T_{RES_CL} with different levels of criticality, we propose a complementary KPI to describe resilience as the time period to be able to supply the city regions at normal power consumption, based on the mean production and storage energy resources in the regions compared with the mean consumption, T_{RES_MC} . For further analysis, we

consider T_{RES_MC} as being 24 hours (full time resilience 24/7, full year, as a proposed target for the future).

III. MODEL FOR SELF-SUFFICIENCY ANALYSIS

The proposed mathematical model for assessing the resilience affordability is based on the general energy flow depicted in Fig. 3, for a full time T_{RES_MC} target.

Fig. 3. General energy flow chart

The following section of the article is dedicated to describe the variables considered in the study and the implemented calculation formulas. The significance of different elements in Fig. 3 is presented below:

$PV1, PV2, PV3$ = The total installed PVs in zones 1, 2 and 3, meaning in the municipality, urban and metropolitan zones illustrated in Fig. 2;

$B1, B2, B3$ = total battery resources for zones 1, 2 and 3;

BC = battery equivalent of the community storage (of all three zones);

$C1, C2, C3$ = Total energy consumed in zones 1, 2 and 3;

Sys = Power system, which can absorb excess energy (E_{to_sys}) or can deliver energy (E_{from_sys});

$E_{PV1}, E_{PV2}, E_{PV3}$ = Energy produced by PVs in zones 1, 2 and 3, respectively;

$E_{sc_PV1}, E_{sc_PV2}, E_{sc_PV3}$ = Self-consumed energy from $PV1, PV2$ and $PV3$, by the consumption of zones 1, 2 and 3;

$E_{sc1_B1}, E_{sc2_B2}, E_{sc3_B3}$ = Self-consumed energy from batteries $B1, B2$ and $B3$, which are charged from $PV1, PV2$ and $PV3$;

$E_{B1_BC}, E_{B2_BC}, E_{B3_BC}$ = Energy of batteries $B1, B2$ and $B3$, which is considered to be virtually transferred in the battery (storage) of the community (of all zones), to be redistributed between zones;

$E_{sys_out1}, E_{sys_out2}, E_{sys_out3}$ = Energy of $PV1, PV2$ and $PV3$ which is an excess not possible to be self-consumed or stored in local batteries, thus is injected in the power grid, for further usage by other consumers;

$E_{sys_in1}, E_{sys_in2}, E_{sys_in3}$ = Energy consumed by $C1, C2$ and $C3$ which cannot be obtained by direct self-consumption from PVs, from storage resources $B1, B2$ and $B3$ or from redistributed storage resources of the community BC , thus need to be purchased from a supplier, from the grid;

$E_{BC_C1}, E_{BC_C2}, E_{BC_C3}$ = Self-consumed energy by $C1, C2$ and $C3$ from the equivalent community battery BC .

In order to determine the system's energy flow, the following formulas have been applied:

Energy produced by $PV1, PV2, PV3$:

$$E_{PV1} = E_{sc_PV1} + E_{pv1_B1} + E_{sys_out1} \quad (1.1)$$

$$E_{PV2} = E_{sc_PV2} + E_{pv2_B2} + E_{sys_out2} \quad (1.2)$$

$$E_{PV3} = E_{sc_PV3} + E_{pv3_B3} + E_{sys_out3} \quad (1.3)$$

Energy absorbed by consumption zones $C1, C2$ and $C3$:

$$E_{C1} = E_{sc_PV1} + E_{sc1_B1} + E_{bc_C1} + E_{sys_in1} \quad (2.1)$$

$$E_{C2} = E_{sc_PV2} + E_{sc2_B2} + E_{bc_C2} + E_{sys_in2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$E_{C3} = E_{sc_PV3} + E_{sc3_B3} + E_{bc_C3} + E_{sys_in3} \quad (2.3)$$

Energy of aggregated storage/battery $B1, B2, B3$:

$$E_{pv1_B1} = E_{sc1_B1} + E_{b1_bc} \quad (3.1)$$

$$E_{pv2_B2} = E_{sc2_B2} + E_{b2_bc} \quad (3.2)$$

$$E_{pv3_B3} = E_{sc3_B3} + E_{b3_bc} \quad (3.3)$$

Energy of aggregated community storage/battery BC :

$$E_{b1_bc} + E_{b2_bc} + E_{b3_bc} = E_{bc_C1} + E_{bc_C2} + E_{bc_C3} \quad (4.1)$$

$$E_{bc} = E_{bc_C1} + E_{bc_C2} + E_{bc_C3} \quad (4.2)$$

Energy bought from the grid (system):

$$E_{bought_from_sys} = E_{sys_in1} + E_{sys_in2} + E_{sys_in3} \quad (5)$$

Energy sold to the grid (system):

$$E_{sold_to_sys} = E_{sys_out1} + E_{sys_out2} + E_{sys_out3} \quad (6)$$

The following constants are considered as known in order to calculate the energy self-consumption:

K_{sc_prod} = Self-consumption factor based on local production, depending on the compatibility between the production and consumption evolution; this value is higher if the ratio between PV production and consumption is low; we consider K_{sc_prod} as being 40%, 25% and 10% from the production in each zone, based on experience and production / consumption ratio.

K_{sc_cons} = Self-consumption factor based on local consumption, depending on the compatibility between the production and consumption evolution; this value is higher if the ratio between PV production and consumption is low; we consider K_{sc_prod} as having the same value in each zone, based on experience and production / consumption ratio, as being 40%.

Standing on these values, we consider the natural self-consumption (without any storage help) as the minimal value between the self-consumption energies based on K_{sc_prod} and K_{sc_cons} .

$$E_{sc1_PV1} = \min(E_{PV1} \times K_{sc_prod1}, E_{C1} \times K_{sc_cons1}) \quad (7.1)$$

$$E_{sc2_PV2} = \min(E_{PV2} \times K_{sc_prod2}, E_{C2} \times K_{sc_cons2}) \quad (7.2)$$

$$E_{sc3_PV3} = \min(E_{PV3} \times K_{sc_prod3}, E_{C3} \times K_{sc_cons3}) \quad (7.3)$$

The energy absorbed by local storage (batteries) is considered to be the minimum between the nominal energy

of the battery and the difference between the consumption and natural self-consumption, if this difference is positive:

$$E_{sc1_B1} = \min(P_{PV1} \times K_{bat1}, E_{C1} - E_{sc1_PV1}) \quad (8.1)$$

$$E_{sc2_B2} = \min(P_{PV2} \times K_{bat2}, E_{C2} - E_{sc2_PV2}) \quad (8.2)$$

$$E_{sc3_B3} = \min(P_{PV3} \times K_{bat3}, E_{C3} - E_{sc3_PV3}) \quad (8.3)$$

or zero, if the $E_{C3} - E_{sc3_PV3} < 0$:

$$E_{sc1_PV1} = 0; E_{sc2_PV2} = 0; E_{sc3_PV3} = 0 \quad (9.1-9.3)$$

The yearly energy stored in the local batteries $B1$, $B2$ and $B3$ is the minimum between the battery capacity and the local production minus natural self-consumption:

$$E_{pv1_B1} = \min(E_{PV1} \times K_{BAT1} \times 365, E_{PV1} - E_{sc1_PV1}) \quad (10.1)$$

$$E_{pv2_B2} = \min(E_{PV2} \times K_{BAT2} \times 365, E_{PV2} - E_{sc2_PV2}) \quad (10.2)$$

$$E_{pv3_B3} = \min(E_{PV3} \times K_{BAT3} \times 365, E_{PV3} - E_{sc3_PV3}) \quad (10.3)$$

The energy available for the community storage is the difference between energy stored in local battery and the one used for local consumption:

$$E_{b1_bc} = E_{pv1_B1} - E_{sc1_B1} \quad (11.1)$$

$$E_{b2_bc} = E_{pv2_B2} - E_{sc2_B2} \quad (11.2)$$

$$E_{b3_bc} = E_{pv3_B3} - E_{sc3_B3} \quad (11.3)$$

Finally, the energy consumed by $C1$, $C2$ and $C3$ from the community battery is given by the formulas:

$$E_{bc_C1} = E_{bc} \times E_{dif_nec1} / E_{dif_nec_tot} \quad (12.1)$$

$$E_{bc_C2} = E_{bc} \times E_{dif_nec2} / E_{dif_nec_tot} \quad (12.2)$$

$$E_{bc_C3} = E_{bc} \times E_{dif_nec3} / E_{dif_nec_tot} \quad (12.3)$$

The energy which is still needed to be consumed from the grid is calculated as the difference from all self-consumed energy (natural, local battery and community battery):

$$E_{sys_in1} = E_{C1} - E_{sc1_PV1} - E_{sc1_B1} - E_{bc_C1} \quad (13.1)$$

$$E_{sys_in2} = E_{C2} - E_{sc2_PV2} - E_{sc2_B2} - E_{bc_C2} \quad (13.2)$$

$$E_{sys_in3} = E_{C3} - E_{sc3_PV3} - E_{sc3_B3} - E_{bc_C3} \quad (13.3)$$

The energy which is still needed to be sold to the grid, as not being possible to be consumed with any of the measures described before, is obtained with the following equations:

$$E_{sys_out1} = E_{PV1} - E_{sc1_PV1} - E_{pv1_B1} - E_{b1_bc} \quad (14.1)$$

$$E_{sys_out2} = E_{PV2} - E_{sc2_PV2} - E_{pv2_B2} - E_{b2_bc} \quad (14.2)$$

$$E_{sys_out3} = E_{PV3} - E_{sc3_PV3} - E_{pv3_B3} - E_{b3_bc} \quad (14.3)$$

The total energy consumed by the three city zones is:

$$E_{c_city} = E_{C1} + E_{C2} + E_{C3} \quad (15)$$

Additionally to the potential of PVs deployment to increase city's resilience, an economic analysis is performed. In this regard, further input data are needed to be established:

$K_{PV_Land1}, K_{PV_Land2}, K_{PV_Land3}$ = Factor of land usage in zone 1, 2, 3 ($z1$ =municipality, $z2$ =urban, $z3$ =metropolitan);
 $S1, S2, S3$ = area of each of the three zones;
 $Sa_{PV_z1}, Sa_{PV_z2}, Sa_{PV_z3}$ = Specific area needed by PVs to obtain 1 kW power;

E_{y_1kW} = energy obtained during a year for 1 kW of PV power. For Bucharest case, the value $E_{y_1kWp} = 1200$ kWh/y has been considered;

$P_{PV1}, P_{PV2}, P_{PV3}$ = total PV power installed in each zone;
 $Proc_cons_{z1,z2,z3}$ = percentage of the overall consumption for each zone; the values chosen for calculation are 80%, 5% and 15%, respectively;

$C_E_basic_{z1,z2,z3,Tot}$ = Cost of energy consumed with basic price, chosen for Romania $P_E_basic = 12c/kWh$;

$C_E_basic = E_{c_city} \times Proc_cons \times P_E_basic$
 $K_{BAT1}, K_{BAT2}, K_{BAT3}$ = the design ratio for battery energy compared with PV power;

$C_{spec_bat_{z1,z2,z3}}$ = specific cost of the battery in Euro/kWh, in each zone;

N_{STOR} = number of storage cycles for the life period;

Ct_{STOR} = cost of storage capacity = $Bat_E \times C_{spec_bat}$

C_{YSTOR} = cost of battery per year = $Ct_{stor} / (N_{stor}/365)$

IV. ASSESSMENT

In the following section the results obtained by implementing the proposed model are presented for the considered scenarios.

Three scenarios are analysed: 50% and 100% coverage of consumption with PV production in the Bucharest area, considering prices for PV and storage investment to be achieved in the period 2020 – 2025 (Scenario 1 and Scenario 2) and 100% consumption coverage considering PV and storage investment to be achieved in period 2025 – 2030. The 5 years timeframes suggest that the exact date of technology maturity can be reached sometime in that period.

TABLE I. SCENARIO 1 INPUTS AND RESULTS (50% CONSUMPTION FROM PV PRODUCTION)

No.	Parameters	Z1	Z2	Z3
1	K_PV_Land1,2,3	2.50%	2.00%	1.65%
2	Sa_PV1,2,3 [m ² /1 kW PV]	10	12	14
3	P_inst_PV [MW]	570	307	2,814
4	Cspec_PV [Eur/kWp]	1500	1200	800
5	Bat_E_ratio [kWh/kWp]	1	1	1
6	Cost_spec_bat [Eur/kWh]	400	320	210
7	Cost of grid en. [c/kWh]	12.00	12.00	12.00
8	Cost of neigh.en. [c/kWh]	15.92	13.83	11.06
9	Price sold en.to grid [c/kWh]	4.00	4.00	4.00
10	E_PV_year [GWh]	684	368	3377.314
Delta cost [Euro]		Resilience Prod/Cons [%]		
No batteries	78,252,724	7.44%	8.03%	50.56%
With batteries	115,159,971	10.96%	23.41%	50.56%

Beside the resilience indicator, the annual cost of electrical energy is also calculated, in order to understand the PVs installation potential and affordability in urban areas.

Table I centralizes the resulted values for the first scenario, which involves the analysis of a production of

around 50% of the total consumption. The 50% self-consumption, considered also as KPI for resilience, is achieved by considering $K_{PV_Land1} = 2.5\%$, $K_{PV_Land2} = 2.0\%$, $K_{PV_Land3} = 1.65\%$, which represent low land factors, easy to be obtained.

The area needed for 1 kW PV power is considered to be lower in central zone 1 (but bringing higher price of the PV module) and higher in the periphery, where more space is available. In this respect, the areas are 10, 12 and 14 m² for 1 kW installed PV, for each of the three zones. The specific price for a 1 kW installation is also considered to be higher in the city and lower in the periphery: 1500, 1200 and 800 Euro/kW installed. Moreover, the specific cost of batteries is considered also to be higher in the city (more constraints) and lower in the periphery, where more space and cheaper solutions to implement are found (line no. 6, with 400, 320 and 210 Euros/kWh installed, which can be considered a medium price value, to be reached in 2020).

The calculations resulted in a slightly higher annual cost of energy by 7.44% if only PVs are installed, respectively of 10.96% higher if batteries are also installed in each zone. The main reason for storage is the increased self-consumption and resilience, latest increasing from 8.03% without storage to 23.41% with storage, while the total yearly cost of energy is only 11% higher.

Fig. 4 shows the energy flow in the case of 50% PV energy production over a year, considering the case with installed batteries. It can be seen that, due to the time difference between peak production and peak consumption, a high portion of the produced energy needs to be sold to the grid ($_{Sys_sell}=2378$ GWh), at low price – during excess energy, and a high portion needs to be purchased in rush hours from the grid ($_{Sys_buy}=6709$ MWh), at high price.

Fig. 4. Energy flow for 50% PV production and with battery resources

As a second scenario, it is considered that the PV production covers 100% the city consumption, by using as PV production areas 3.5%, 2.5% and 3% for the city zones.

The assessment from Table II shows that producing the entire need of energy in Bucharest area (101.75%), gives medium increase of energy costs per year, in both situations: without batteries (15.73%) and with batteries (25.14%). However, the situation with batteries increases the resilience from 13% to 36.3%, which is 13% higher than in scenario 1.

Fig. 5 shows the energy flow in the case of 100% PV energy production over a year. Finally, an additional scenario of 100% RES is analysed, leading to an even higher resilience level, by considering the trends of battery storage and PV price reduction in the year 2025 horizon, which brings the possibility of increased storage investment in each zone and lower overall costs.

TABLE II. SCENARIO 2 INPUTS AND RESULTS (100% CONSUMPTION FROM PV PRODUCTION)

	Parameters	Z1	Z2	Z3
1	K_PV_Land1,2,3	3.50%	2.50%	3.00%
2	Sa_PV1,2,3 [m ² /1 kW PV]	8	10	12
3	P_inst_PV [MW]	998	460	5,970
4	Cspec_PV [Eur/kWp]	1500	1200	800
5	Bat_E_ratio [kWh/kWp]	0.8	0.8	0.74
6	Cost_spec_bat [Eur/kWh]	400	320	210
7	Cost of grid en. [c/kWh]	12.00	12.00	12.00
8	Cost of neigh.en. [c/kWh]	15.92	13.83	11.06
9	Price sold en.to grid [c/kWh]	4.00	4.00	4.00
10	E_PV_year [GWh]	1197	552	7164
Delta cost [Euro]		Resilience Prod/Cons [%]		
No batteries	165,340,500	15.73%	13.04%	101.75%
With batteries	264,314,083	25.14%	36.31%	101.75%

Fig. 5. Energy flow for 100% PV production and with battery resources

Table III shows the scenario data for more advanced and affordable storage and PV technologies in 2025.

TABLE III. SCENARIO 3 INPUTS AND RESULTS (100% CONS. FROM PV PROD., LOWER PRICE FOR STORAGE)

	Parameters	Z1	Z2	Z3
1	K_PV_Land1,2,3	3.50%	2.50%	3.00%
2	Sa_PV1,2,3 [m ² /1 kW PV]	8	10	12
3	P_inst_PV [MW]	998	460	5,970
4	Cspec_PV [Eur/kWp]	1200	1000	500
5	Bat_E_ratio [kWh/kWp]	1.973	2.466	2.98
6	Cost_spec_bat [Eur/kWh]	250	200	100
7	Cost of grid en. [c/kWh]	12.00	12.00	12.00
8	Cost of neigh.en. [c/kWh]	13.83	12.44	8.97
9	Price sold en.to grid [c/kWh]	4.00	4.00	4.00
10	E_PV_year [GWh]	1197	552	7164
Delta cost [Euro]		Resilience Prod/Cons [%]		
No batteries	-16,513,667	-1.57%	13.04%	101.75%
With batteries	-34,233,868	-3.26%	100.09%	101.75%

The table shows that for future low prices of batteries, the resilience can increase up to 100%, which is an equivalent of one full day of self-consumption using only the three local zone resources. In fact, at these prices it is a parity effect which pays the storage means due to complete self-consumption of cheaper local energy production. Fig. 6 shows the energy flow in the case of 100% PV energy production with low price batteries which allow 100% resilience.

Fig. 6. Energy flow for 100% PV production, low price battery

The figure shows that there is nearly zero sell and buy energy exchange with the system (*Sys_sell* and *Sys_buy* values are very low), showing that it is ensured a full self-consumption over a year and a 100% overall resilience. It means also yearly average energy independence, allowing circular economy and finally long-term sustainability.

Several assumptions have been considered in the scenario, using a simplified model to give more a general view of the RES production and its influence on the smart city resilience rather than aiming for precise calculations: all consumptions and productions are placed in low voltage network; the distribution + taxes fee for self-consumption are very low, being considered only the system tariff; the self-consumption ratio over a year are based on statistical factors and on experience; inter-zones energy exchange has a cumulated grid and city taxation of 5 cents/kWh; average energy produced from 1 kW PV is 1200 kWh; the PV panels investment is paid in 12 years (considered as a strategical investment rather than a bankable opportunity).

Fig. 7 gives an overall view of the three scenarios. It suggests that smart cities with local PV production, storage and self-consumption show feasibility with the expected costs of technologies in 2020-2025 and 2025-2030, thus requiring further attention for a more detailed analysis.

Fig. 7. Overview of the three scenarios

V. CONCLUSIONS

The conducted assessment shows that coverage with PV production of the energy consumption in Bucharest areas (50% and 100%) is possible, giving only small increase of

the yearly energy costs in both situations, while the resilience is increasing from 39% in the first scenario (50% PV) to 64% and 89% (100% PV), depending on the used storage resources and the evolution of their price. The study suggests that, for specific prices and characteristics of PVs and batteries chosen as inputs (2020-2025-2030), is possible to have the same yearly costs as in the basic case, but obtaining increased resilience and clean energy production. The simplified model shows that grid-parity can be attended (price from the grid versus price of energy produced in the three zones), allowing the deployment of low carbon and high resilience energy solution based on self-consumption.

More refinements will be made in future work, but this preliminary study gives a promising perspective for having a resilient city with most of the energy obtained locally, from PVs and local and community storage resources. It shows the feasibility of a resilient Bucharest city, with similar costs in the yearly budget for the energy acquisition. Other aspects of battery expansion, e.g. recycling aspects at the end of life are already in study (e.g. in [18]) and end-customer future price advantage for the translation towards 100% renewables [19] will be subject of future work for the authors.

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